

Long-Term Preservation Policy Template

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1. Objectives, scope and delimitation of this policy

- 1.1. The general aim of this preservation policy is to ensure the authentic and trustworthy preservation and accessibility of digital research data and related outputs, henceforth referred to as “datasets”, for reuse in the long term.
- 1.2. The specific aims of the preservation policy are to:
 - Provide authentic and reliable instances of datasets to researchers;
 - Maintain the integrity and quality of the datasets;
 - Ensure that datasets are managed throughout their lifecycle (e.g. when migrations or changes in metadata are carried out) in the medium that is most appropriate for the task they perform;
 - Ensure that the relevant level of information security is applied to each dataset;
- 1.3. The scope of this policy is limited to [LTP Institution]’s service for long-term preservation, [LTP Service]. It applies exclusively to datasets held in [LTP Service]. This policy does not consider preservation of other materials, such as [LTP Institution]’s web pages, internal and external documents, and digital objects in any other services the [LTP Institution] provides.

- 1.4. The [LTP Institution] assumes responsibility for the long-term preservation and accessibility of datasets ingested (by individual deposits or bulk data transfers) into its [LTP Service].
- 1.5. Long-term preservation and provision of sustained access to datasets fits within the remit and mission of [LTP Institution].
- 1.6. The length of the preservation period is ... <specify the preservation period in years or "indefinite">, unless legal obligations prevent this (as described in article 4.7).
- 1.7. [LTP Service] is designed to preserve data in a way that can be assessed by and is useful for the designated communities it intends to serve. This target audience consists of ... <specify the designated communities, such as scientific domains, research communities, or research in general>.

2. Ingest

This section distinguishes two situations, to which partly different articles apply:

- A. [LTP Service] is provided by the repository or data service itself. In this situation, the ingest takes place via deposits by researchers or research communities into the repository, which also acts as [LTP Service]. Researchers or research communities are the depositors.
- B. [LTP Service] is provided by an external organisation / separate [LTP Institution]. In this situation, the ingest consists of (bulk) data transfers from the repository to the external [LTP Service]. The repository/data service acts as the depositor on behalf of the researchers and research communities, who originally deposited the datasets. A Long-Term Preservation Agreement (LTP Agreement) describing the particulars of the responsibilities of both parties involved will be necessary.

Note that the choice between situation A and B also has repercussions for the ways in which the access to datasets will be arranged (see section 7). For further considerations on outsourcing LTP refer to section 1.3.1 of the report.

2A. [LTP Service] is provided by the data service itself

- 2.1. The datasets, including metadata as supplied by the depositor [= researcher or research community], are considered by [LTP service] as the Submission Information Package (SIP) in OAIS terms. This is the "original" information to be stored for long-term preservation.
- 2.2. The datasets are professionally cataloged according to the metadata standard used by [LTP Service].

- 2.3. [LTP Service] supports a list of licenses for open data sharing, from which a selection can be made by the depositor during ingestion. A list of supported licenses is available [provide reference; for an example see Appendix 6].
- 2.4. [LTP Service] provides a Persistent Identifier [PID] to each ingested [dataset / file / object] <indicate to which units the PID apply> for long-term reference to their location.
- 2.5. The quality control of the metadata is maintained as follows:
- The datasets that the [LTP Service] ingests are accompanied by metadata as supplied by the [Depositor], which should be adequate to enable the designated communities to understand and reuse the content for analytical and research purposes.
 - The deposited datasets (including metadata) are checked and validated by [LTP service] according to documented data ingest procedures, including the following checks <indicate what applies>:
 - Virus scans
 - Completeness of data (e.g. checksums)
 - Metadata and additional documentation
 - Compliance with preferred / accepted formats
 - Organisation of data (data structure), reformatting
 - Presence of personal data
 - Data cleaning
 - Other: ... <specify>
 - In order to guarantee minimal metadata quality, only records that comply with the following basic Dublin Core Metadata Terms¹ can be successfully ingested into [LTP Service] <indicate which terms minimally apply>:
 - Title
 - Creator
 - Description
 - Date (created)
 - Rights
 - Audience
 - ... <specify more terms if applicable>
 - The completeness and accuracy of the metadata accompanying the deposited dataset is the responsibility of the depositor.
 - [LTP Service] may notify the depositor of deficiencies and inaccuracies in the metadata (during or after ingestion).
 - Alternatively, if datasets or metadata contain deficiencies, [LTP Service] can make alterations post ingest. Hereby distinction is made between minor and major alterations to digital assets:

¹ See DCMI terms: <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

- Major: when a digital object in a dataset is changed, this will result in a new version and therefore a new dataset with a new PID in [LTP service]. The new and the old version are cross-referenced in their respective descriptive metadata, and the new version will be the default version for access.
- Minor: when there is a change (addition or edit) in the metadata, descriptive documents or supplementary files, this is documented in the (administrative) metadata, no new dataset is created and no new persistent identifier is minted.

2B. [LTP Service] is provided by an external organisation / separate [LTP Institution]

- 2.6. The datasets, including metadata as supplied by depositor [= data service], are considered by [LTP service] as the Submission Information Package (SIP) in OAIS terms. This is the “original” information to be stored for long-term preservation in the [LTP Service].
- 2.7. The datasets are professionally catalogued according to the metadata standard used by [LTP Service].
- 2.8. Licenses for open data sharing attributed to the datasets are ingested “as is”, and are preserved and supported unchanged by [LTP service]. A list of supported licenses is available [provide reference; for an example see Appendix 6].
- 2.9. Persistent Identifiers [PIDs] minted by the [data service] are ingested into the [LTP Service] “as is”, and continue to refer to the original location of the data (see section 7 on Access for changes in the case [data service] ceases to exist).
- 2.10. [LTP Service] will allocate additional PIDs for reference to archived copies of the data sets in [LTP Service] (see section 7 on Access for alternatives in referencing for access to datasets).
- 2.11. The quality control of the metadata is maintained as follows:
- The datasets that the [LTP Service] ingests are accompanied by metadata as supplied by the [Depositor], which should be adequate to enable the designated communities to understand and reuse the content for analytical and research purposes.
 - The deposited datasets (including metadata) are checked and validated by [LTP service] according to documented data ingest procedures, including the following checks <indicate what applies>:

- Virus scans
 - Completeness of data (e.g. checksums)
 - Metadata and additional documentation
 - Compliance with preferred / accepted formats
 - Organisation of data (data structure), reformatting
 - Presence of personal data
 - Data cleaning
 - Other: ... <specify>
- Metadata fields of the [data service] are mapped with the fields of the [LTP Service] metadata schema:
- Corresponding fields (from the same metadata scheme) are copied
 - Similar fields (from different metadata schemes) are mapped wherever possible
 - Fields that cannot be mapped are stored with the dataset as additional documentation (in a separate metadata blob file).
- In order to guarantee minimal metadata quality, only datasets that comply with the following basic Dublin Core Metadata Terms² can be successfully ingested into [LTP Service] <indicate which terms minimally apply>:
- Title
 - Creator
 - Description
 - Date (created)
 - Rights
 - Audience
 - ... <specify more terms if desired>
- The completeness and accuracy of the metadata ingested from [data service] into [LTP Service] is the responsibility of the [data service].
- [LTP Service] may notify the [data service] of deficiencies and inaccuracies in the metadata (during or after ingestion).
- Alternatively, if datasets or metadata contain deficiencies, [LTP Service] can make alterations post ingest. Hereby distinction is made between minor and major alterations to digital assets:
- Major: when a digital object in a dataset is changed, this will result in a new version and therefore a new dataset with a new PID in [LTP service]. The new and the old version are cross-referenced in their respective descriptive metadata, and the new version will be the default version for access.

² See DCMI terms: <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

- Minor: when there is a change (addition or edit) in the metadata, descriptive documents or supplementary files, this is documented in the (administrative) metadata, no new dataset is created and no new persistent identifier is minted.

3. Archival Storage

- 3.1. The ingested datasets (data and metadata) constitute the basis for the Archival Information Package (AIP) in OAIS terms. Archival actions related to the custody of AIPs, which may affect the chain of provenance, will be documented, including changes in <indicate what applies>:
 - ... the archival system (upgrades, new systems)
 - ... documentation standards
 - ... license definitions
 - ... file formats (format conversions and updates)
 - ... storage location (migrations to other facilities)
 - ... other <specify other archival actions influencing the chain of provenance>
- 3.2. The archival storage function receives AIPs from the ingest function and adds them to the permanent storage facility, and oversees the management of this storage, including media monitoring and refreshment. This ensures that AIPs will be retrievable and can be disseminated over time.
- 3.3. [LTP Service] does not assume responsibility for the preservation of data that are hosted externally, unless this is specifically agreed with an external storage provider, to be specified in an agreement (as in article 3.5).
- 3.4. The [LTP Institution] is committed to take all necessary precautions to ensure the physical integrity and security of the datasets stored in its [LTP Service], including <indicate which measures apply>:
 - Periodic technology-vulnerability scans
 - SLAs with external IT providers, e.g. for data storage
 - Procedures for file fixity checking (checksums), verifying that data have not been altered or corrupted
 - A confidentiality statement for [LTP Service] staff (as described in article 6.6.4)
 - Periodic security audits
 - Other measures: ... <specify>
- 3.5. [LTP Institution] may outsource the physical data storage to an external storage provider, provided it has a contract and accompanying Service Level Agreement (SLA) with its provider, which include <indicate what applies>:

- A confidentiality statement
- A quality assurance guarantee (see also article 2.6).
- An information security policy and security measures.
- Error checking routines and error solving procedures.
- A disaster recovery procedure.
- A monitoring policy of servers and storage media, and the timely refreshment of media.
- A performance reporting mechanism.
- A backup policy.
- Storage of at least two copies in physically and geographically different locations.
- Other: ... <specify>

4. Data Management

- 4.1. [LTP Service] maintains a catalogue of metadata which uses a standard schema for describing its contents. This database is searchable by internal and external finding aids.
 - 4.2. The Archival Information Package includes administrative metadata which support archival operations, including change or version control of datasets.
 - 4.3. [LTP Institution] guarantees the timeliness, authenticity and integrity of the datasets in its [LTP Service] for future access and reuse.
- The datasets (and metadata) ingested (including exact and integral copies thereof) are considered as „original“ and authentic.
 - If preservation and/or dissemination copies in derived formats are made (e.g. preserved formats or lower resolution video formats for web viewing), these will be stored alongside the originals.
 - Provenance information is supplied for all copies in preservation and dissemination formats that can be traced back to the original datasets as ingested.
 - Authenticity and integrity of Archival Information Packages (AIPs) imply that once a dataset is ingested into the [LTP Service], the AIP can not be changed or removed by the user.
 - Only authorized staff of [LTP Institution] have the right to modify the format and/or functionality of an archived object, if this is deemed necessary to facilitate the digital sustainability, distribution or re-use of the information it contains.

- [LTP Institution] ensures that any alteration to the preserved version of any part of a dataset will only take place under controlled conditions and will be accurately documented. Hence, the content stored in [LTP Service] is of a static nature.
 - When datasets are updated, changed or extended, the resulting new versions are considered and treated as new assets.
- The chain of custody of datasets archived in the [LTP Service] is documented through metadata, which guarantee that all archival actions are explicit, complete, correct and current.
- 4.4. [LTP Service] maintains (or conforms to) a documented list of <indicate what applies>:
- ... preferred or archival formats, about which [LTP Service] is dedicated to offer long-term guarantees in terms of future findability, accessibility and reusability³.
 - ... accepted formats, which are preserved in the format as ingested, for which the findability and accessibility are guaranteed, but for which the future reusability can not be guaranteed.
- 4.5. [LTP Service] monitors the potential obsolescence of file formats and has conversion policies and procedures in place to take action when required.
- 4.6. In case of conversion of objects to another (preferred or archival) file format (e.g. for preservation or access purposes), the [LTP Service] will also maintain the original file(s) <indicate what applies>:
- Files stored in the [LTP Service] from outdated formats are migrated to successor formats, and the archival metadata is updated accordingly.
 - Files in outdated formats are preserved to maintain the chain of provenance.
- 4.7. Datasets or files that are archived, published and/or exposed in the [LTP Service] can only be deleted or made inaccessible by [LTP Institution]'s authorized staff for compelling reasons:
- If the content is unlawful.
 - If there is a legally binding maximum preservation period for the content.
 - If personal data appears to be preserved without permission of research subjects.

³ The Interoperability of datasets depends on characteristics of the data that are partly beyond the control of [LTP service] and can therefore not be guaranteed by [LTP Service]. The Interoperability of research data is the responsibility of the researcher / research community.

- If the content consists of personal data, and a research subject rightfully objects to the preservation of a digital object with an appeal to the GDPR (e.g. right to be forgotten; or revocation of informed consent).
 - Other compelling reasons, to be decided by the director of the [LTP Institution].
- 4.8. In case a data object needs to be deleted, this is recorded in the metadata, which will continue to exist as a “tombstone” record.

5. Administration⁴

- 5.1. [LTP Institution] monitors the operations of its [LTP Service] and publishes periodic reports on its performance. [An example of a monitoring schedule is provided in Appendix 2].
- 5.2. [LTP Institution] develops a multi-annual strategy which includes the strategic direction and upgrading of the [LTP Service].
- 5.3. The planning and control cycle of [LTP Institution] is overseen by ... <specify how or by whom the planning and control cycle is monitored>.
- 5.4. The strategy and functioning of [LTP Institution] is subject to periodic external evaluations, the reports of which are available publicly / on request / otherwise: ... <specify what applies>.
- 5.5. A(n) (scientific) advisory board consisting of prominent members of the designated community advises [LTP Institution] on its strategic course and development.
- 5.6. [LTP Institution] maintains functions for providing customer support.
- 5.7. [LTP Institution] maintains a publicly available list and description of legal and statutory regulations which apply (see Appendix 3 for an overview of generally applicable European and national laws and regulations; select which specific regulations apply):
- General Terms and Conditions of Use
 - Data Deposit Agreement
 - Long-Term Preservation Agreement
 - Data Processing Agreements
 - User licenses
 - Privacy policy
 - Liability statement
 - Ownership rights statement

⁴ Note that several Administrative functions of the OAIS model are dealt with in other sections of this policy:

Other applicable regulations: ... <specify>

6. Preservation Planning

- 6.1. [LTP Institution] monitors the contents of its [LTP Service] and periodically publishes metrics on key performance indicators.
- 6.2. [LTP Institution] reviews its preferred and/or accepted formats list and guidelines periodically for obsolescence and completeness, updating and extending them as needed.
- 6.3. [LTP Institution] performs the following other monitoring functions for preservation planning <indicate which monitoring activities apply>:
- Monitoring security risks, in order to anticipate and control such risks.
 - Technology watch, in order to recommend adaptations in its technology environment, in particular its archival system(s).
 - Monitoring changes in service requirements of its Designated Communities.
 - Other monitoring activities: ... <specify>
- 6.4. Roles and responsibilities, confidentiality, limited liability <indicate what applies>:
- The Director of [LTP Institution] is responsible for maintaining this policy.
 - The staff of [LTP Institution] implements this policy as appropriate to their roles and responsibilities.
 - Preservation decisions about the [LTP Service] are made within the context of the [LTP Institution]'s mission and strategy, balancing the constraints of costs, scholarly value, user accessibility, and legal admissibility.
 - [LTP Institution]'s staff, including temporary staff, trainees, (visiting) fellows and volunteers, are accountable for keeping confidentiality when processing digital assets stored in [LTP Service], in particular personal data, in any way whatsoever, by signing a confidentiality statement.
 - This policy will be evaluated and, if necessary, will be revised every ... years <specify the evaluation and revision cycle>, or as soon as security threats, changes in technology or legal and statutory context require to do so.
 - [LTP Institution] is not liable for the contents, including errors, of research data ingested into its [LTP Service], nor for (possible errors in) the metadata and additional documentation associated with those datasets. [LTP Institution] is also not liable for incorrect inferences resulting from the analysis of those datasets.
- 6.5. Funding and contingency plan:
- [LTP Institution] declares it receives adequate funding to fulfil its mission, which includes the maintenance of the [LTP Service].

- In case of dissolution of the [LTP Institution], it has a continuity plan in place which guarantees that a successor organization will take over the care of the [LTP service]⁵.

7. Access

As in the Ingest section (2), this section distinguishes two different situations, to which partly different articles apply:

- A. [LTP Service] is provided by the [data service] itself. In this situation, the access takes place through access mechanisms of the [Data Service].
- B. [LTP Service] is provided by an external organisation / separate [LTP Institution]. In this situation, the [data service] needs to indicate in the LTP Agreement whether it wants the datasets in [LTP Service] to be exposed (= to be findable and/or accessible) for end users via the [LTP Service] or not.

If for any reason the original [data service] is discontinued, the access function to the datasets of [data service], as ingested and preserved by [LTP Institution], will be taken over by the [LTP Service]. In this situation two extra articles apply (7.6 and 7.7).

7.1. [LTP Service] provides the following access functions <indicate what applies>:

- A user interface for browsing and searching its content
- An API using an open and universal protocol (e.g. OAI-PMH: Open Archives Initiative: Protocol for Metadata Harvesting)
- Other: ... <specify>

7.2. Metadata in [LTP Service] are always openly accessible, i.e. without copy- or database-rights and without authentication or authorisation of users (either through the user interface or via the API).

⁵ This is in conformance to the mandatory OAIS requirements and CTS requirement 3 "Continuity of access: The repository has a continuity plan to ensure ongoing access to and preservation of its holdings". For example, in the case of DANS: The NWO-KNAW *Samenwerkingsovereenkomst DANS* (Collaboration Agreement DANS) 2015 explicitly states that, in the case of discontinuity of DANS, NWO and KNAW will take over the responsibility for the digital assets archived at DANS and store these elsewhere "in the most responsible manner possible and under equivalent technical conditions" (article 10.6 of the Collaboration Agreement).

- 7.3. Users need to register (create an account) and to login to the [LTP Service] if the license to view and download files requires them to do so.
- 7.4. Authentication by registration and logging in is not obligatory for viewing or downloading data with licences equivalent to full Open Access (CC0 Waiver).
- 7.5. In order to enable reuse, data released from [LTP Service] are always accompanied by <indicate what applies>:
- A clear conditions of use statement conforming to the applicable licence or CC0 waiver.
 - A standard citation recommendation to encourage proper data citation.
 - Other: ... <specify>

Article 7.6 and 7.7 only apply in case [LTP Service] is provided by an external organisation / separate [LTP Institution] as described under situation B in the text box above.

- 7.6. By default, as long as the [data service] exists and its content is accessible for end users, the standard PID assigned by [data service] to a dataset archived in the [LTP Service] refers to the location in the original [data service].
- 7.7. In case the [data service] ceases to exist and becomes inaccessible for end users, the access to the datasets stored at the [LTP Service] will become findable and accessible via the search and download functions of [LTP Service], under similar access conditions and licenses as in the original [data service].